

**A STUDY ON ASSESSMENT OF THE PRESENCE OF AAM IN 30
O.P.D PATIENTS OF ROGA NIDAN DEPARTMENT OF
GOVERNMENT AYURVEDIC COLLEGE AND HOSPITAL,
GUWAHATI**

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Article Received on 16 Jan. 2026,
Article Revised on 05 Feb. 2026,
Article Published on 15 Feb. 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18660033>

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How to cite this Article: *¹Dr. Manisha Pathak,
²Dr. Anup Baishya (2026). A Study On
Assessment Of The Presence Of Aam In 30
O.P.D Patients Of Roga Nidan Department Of
Government Ayurvedic College And Hospital,
Guwahati. World Journal of Pharmaceutical
Research, 15(4), 713-717.

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda the ancient science of living a healthy and long life believes that prevention of disease is better than cure. Ayurveda further emphasises on importance of proper diagnostic technique and in this regard this science mentioned various diagnostic tools to assess pathological condition at early stages. Aam pariksha is an important pariksha in Ayurveda to determine the presence of toxins in the body. The concept of Aam pariksha, a diagnostic technique of Ayurveda is mentioned in Ayurvedic classics like Charak Samhita, Astanga Hridaya and Madhav Nidan. Darsan (inspection), prashnam (questioning), sparsanam (palpation) etc are methods used in Ayurveda for disease identification.

KEYWORDS: Aam pariksha is an important pariksha in Ayurveda to determine the presence of toxins in the body.

INTRODUCTION

The Rasa dhatu is poorly formed when the function of Jatharagni is weakened or hampered due to intake of improper food. Due to poor digestion, improperly formed metabolic product residing in the Amashaya is termed as Aam.^[1] In Ayurveda Aam is considered the root cause of all the diseases.^[2] The presence or absence of Aam in the body can be assessed by inspection, questioning and palpation. The presence of Aam in the body can be determined by

several signs. These are obstruction of urine, stool, sweat, loss of strength, heaviness of the body, reduced movement of vayu in the body, laziness, impaired digestion, production of sputum, tastelessness, exhaustion without any activity, thick white or yellow coating on the tongue.^[3] By assessment of presence or absence of Aam in general O.P.D patients we can conclude the role of Aam in almost all the diseases.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A clinical study was done on 30 O.P.D patients randomly selected at Roga Nidan department of Government Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Guwahati, Assam as per necessary formalities under strict protocol to prevent bias and reduce the error in the study. Detailed history regarding the signs as mentioned in Ayurveda classics were taken into consideration in a specially designed proforma. All the patients between 18 to 60 years of age were included in the study excluding the pregnant women and critically ill patients.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

1. All the signs of Aam mentioned as per the Ayurveda classics were taken under consideration.
2. For accurate assessment, the questionnaire have been employed as follows.
 - a) Frequency of signs once in a month = 0
 - b) Frequency of signs once in a week = 1
 - c) Frequency of signs 2-3 days in a week = 2
 - d) Frequency of signs 4 days in a week = 3
 - e) Frequency of signs 5 days in a week = 4
 - f) Frequency of signs everyday = 5
3. For assessment, the signs of Aam have been put in a specially designed proforma
4. Data above 50% of occurrence rate have been taken into consideration for the study.

OBSERVATION AND STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

No. of patients among the 30 patients who showed signs of Aam = 30

Table 01: Table showing presence or absence of Aam according to disease of patients.

Sl. No.	Disease	No. of patients observed	Aam Present/ Absent
1.	Fever	2	Present
2.	Sciatica	3	Present
3.	Frozen Shoulder	3	Present
4.	Cervical Spondylosis	2	Present

5.	Psoriasis	3	Present
6.	Eczema	1	Present
7.	IVDP	3	Present
8.	Tennis Elbow	1	Present
9.	Cough	2	Present
10.	Constipation	1	Present
11.	Ascitis	2	Present
12.	Fatty liver	1	Present
13.	IBS	2	Present
14.	Diarrhea	2	Present
15.	Diabetes	2	Present

Table 02: Prevalence of Signs in the patients in the study.

Sl. no.	Signs of Aam	No. of patients sign is observed	Percentage of No. of patients sign is observed	No. of observations as per frequency	Percentage of No. of observations as per frequency(%)
1.	Obstruction of urine, stool, sweat	6	20	18	12
2.	Loss of strength	18	60	54	36
3.	Heaviness of body	8	26.6	21	14
4.	Reduced movement of Vayu in the body	21	70	96	64
5.	Laziness	19	63.3	92	61.3
6.	Impaired digestion	13	43.3	36	24
7.	Production of Sputum	7	23.3	20	13.3
8.	Tastelessness	19	63.3	90	60
9.	Exhaustion without any activities	5	16.6	18	12
10.	Thick white or yellow coating of tongue	12	40	36	24

Charts showing Prevalence of Signs in the patients in the study

DISCUSSION

The assessment of presence or absence of signs of Aam is done on 30 patients of Roga Nidan O.P.D of Government Ayurvedic College and Hospital. About 10 signs of Aam has been mentioned in the Ayurveda classics.

Among the 30 patients who were selected randomly for the assessment of Aam, all the 30 patients showed symptoms of Aam.

The signs present in above 50% of the patients are reduced movement of vayu in the body (70%), laziness (63.3%), tastelessness (63.3%), loss of strength (60%).

The percentage of Number of observations as per frequency of presence of sign which are above 50% are reduced movement of vayu in the body (64%), laziness (61.3), tastelessness (60%).

CONCLUSION

The present study indicates that Aam is present in all the patients hence we can conclude that Aam is the root cause of all the diseases.

The signs of Aam like reduced movement of vayu in the body, laziness, tastelessness, loss of strength are seen in more than 50% of the patients.

The present study is done in a small group of people, if the study is carried out in a large group of people it can be established that Aam is the root cause of all the diseases.

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